

Detection Schemes for Integrated SWIPT Receivers with Non-Linear Energy Harvesting

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Abstract—Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) is an emerging technology to connect and energize devices wirelessly, in the future Internet of Things (IoT) and wireless sensor networks (WSN). In this paper, we investigate two coherent detection schemes for integrated SWIPT receivers. At first, we examine a single input multiple output (SIMO) topology, with multiple rectennas at the receiver’s side, i.e. MRCA scheme. Targeting to reduce the decoding complexity, we further investigate a single input single output (SISO) topology, with one receive antenna connected to multiple rectifiers, i.e. MRCE scheme. A non-linear energy harvesting (EH) model, is considered for both schemes, by taking into account the sensitivity and saturation effects of rectifiers. With the use of maximum likelihood (ML) and soft decoding, energy detection is succeeded. An asymptotic analysis is conducted for both schemes, providing upper and lower bounds for EH and information decoding, respectively. Simulation and experimental results along with theoretical analysis, validate the enhanced performance of the proposed schemes.

Keywords—SWIPT, integrated receiver, non-linear energy harvesting, coherent detection, soft decoding.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the new era of the Internet of Things (IoT), wireless power transfer (WPT) has been recognized as a promising technology to overcome the critical challenge of supplying power, remotely and wirelessly, to an extensive number of low-power IoT devices [1]. Specifically, radio-frequency (RF) signals are considered as a viable source for WPT, since they have the ability to energize devices over a long distance. On the other hand, RF signals have been widely used for wireless information transmission. Therefore, a simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) system, is considered an appealing solution for IoT networks.

In a SWIPT system there are two fundamental architectures, [2], regarding the receiver. In the first one, the received signal is split into two parts, either in the time or in the power domain. One part is used for information transfer and another part for energy harvesting (EH). In the second architecture, an integrated information decoding (ID) and EH circuit is considered. The idea was introduced in [3] for a point-to-point system. Specifically, the RF to baseband conversion is replaced

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by a rectifying antenna (rectenna), which receives and converts the RF signal to direct current (DC) power that is used both for EH and ID. A benefit of this architecture, is that by replacing the active RF to baseband conversion with a passive rectifier, it can reduce the power consumption of a SWIPT receiver.

SWIPT is an emerging technology for IoT, has attracted significant interests in the communication literature and numerous studies have been conducted in various disciplines. An important area to be explored, is the various detection schemes for decoding information. In particular, the authors in [4] study the intermodulation of multi-frequency transmission signal by exploiting both the amplitude and the phase. In [5], a pulse position modulation, where information is encoded in the position of the pulse, is investigated. Considering that the rectifying process from RF to DC is similar to an envelope detection process, ID is succeeded by detecting the power variations in the received signal adopting tone-index multisine modulation [6] or enhanced biased amplitude-shift keying [7].

Motivated by the above, in this paper, we study SWIPT considering an integrated architecture at the receiver’s side, while adopting energy detection for ID. The main contribution of this paper, is to study the fundamental capacity of integrated SWIPT receiver by adopting two simple topologies. Specifically, targeting to improve the system performance, in terms of both EH and ID, we initially consider a single input multiple output (SIMO) topology, with multiple rectennas at the receiver’s side, i.e. MRCA scheme. We further explore a single input single output (SISO) topology, with one receive antenna connected to multiple rectifiers, i.e. MRCE scheme. This technique has been considered in the literature, in the context of a separated EH [8], resulting to enhanced EH for a SISO topology. Simulation and experimental results fully validate the theoretical analysis and confirm the benefits of the the proposed schemes, in terms of enhanced EH and ID.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Network Model

We consider a SWIPT system, with a single antenna transmitter and multiple antennas, N , at the receiver’s side. The source transmits a baseband signal $x(t)$ with $\mathbb{E}[x^2(t)] = 1$. The modulation scheme used is on-off keying (OOK), while symbols $x \in [0, 1]$, are transmitted with equal probability. Then the up-converted RF signal is transmitted over a Rayleigh fading channel. The received power signal at each antenna is

Fig. 1. Integrated SWIPT receiver, MRCA scheme.

equal to $u_i = |\sqrt{P}h_i x + n_i|^2$, where P is the transmitted power and $i \in [1, N]$. With h_i , we denote the channel coefficient, which is modeled as a complex Gaussian random variable with zero mean and unit variance, while, n_i models the noise as an additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with unit variance. The received power signal, u_i , is exponentially distributed, with a rate parameter $\lambda_x = 1/(Px^2 + 1)$. Therefore, the relative probability density function (pdf) is

$$f(u_i) = \lambda_x \exp(-\lambda_x u_i). \quad (1)$$

Depending on the transmitted symbol x , we consider in our analysis, two rate parameters, i.e. $\lambda_0 = 1$ and $\lambda_1 = 1/(P+1)$.

At the receiver's side, we consider an integrated SWIPT architecture, where the rectified DC power signal is split into two parts, for ID and EH, with power ratio ρ . In order to reduce the energy requirements for the symbol detection and jointly maximize the power split for EH, we consider that $\rho \rightarrow 0$ [2]. As seen in Fig. 1, the first topology consists of multiple receive antennas N , each one connected to a rectifier. This way, the decoder samples one rectenna in order to conduct ID and EH. In the second topology, Fig. 2, we assume one receive antenna, i.e. $N = 1$, connected to N_R rectifiers. The received power signal u_1 , is equally split to N_o rectification circuits, where $N_o \in [1, N_R]$. Considering that the rectifiers exhibit the same characteristics, the decoder samples only one of the DC outputs for ID, while for the EH all the activated rectifiers N_o , should be considered.

B. Energy Harvesting and Decoding Model

Regarding the EH, we consider a constant-linear-constant (CLC) model [9]. The non-linearity between DC and RF power is described as

$$y_i(u_i) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } u_i < u_{min}, \\ \alpha(u_i - u_{min}), & \text{if } u_{min} \leq u_i < u_{max}, \\ \alpha(u_{max} - u_{min}), & \text{if } u_{max} \leq u_i, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where u_{min} and u_{max} , denote the sensitivity and saturation levels of the rectifier, respectively. When $u_i < u_{min}$, the output of the rectifier is in the sensitivity area, while when $u_i > u_{max}$ it reaches the saturation area, where the DC output is maximized. Finally, parameter $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ denotes the conversion efficiency.

Considering that channel state information is available at the receiver, coherent detection is adopted. The transmitted

Fig. 2. Integrated SWIPT receiver, MRCE scheme.

symbol is detected with the use of ML and soft decoding, based on vector \mathbf{y} and the symbol which yields the maximum conditioned density $f(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{u}^x)$, i.e.

$$\tilde{x} = \arg \max_{x \in (0,1)} f(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{u}^x), \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{u}^x , denote the DC and RF power signals from the N rectifiers, given that x is transmitted. Assuming that noise is independent between different receive antennas, $f(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{u}^x)$ can be factored like

$$f(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{u}^x) = \prod_{i=1}^N f(y_i|u_i^x), \quad (4)$$

where $f(y_i|u_i^x)$ denotes the conditional pdf of y_i given u_i , considering that x is transmitted, $\forall i \in [1, N]$. From (1),

$$f(y_i|u_i^x) = \begin{cases} (1 - e^{-\lambda_x u_{min}}) \delta(y_i(u_i)), & \text{if } y_i(u_i) = 0, \\ \frac{\lambda_x}{\alpha} e^{-\lambda_x (\frac{y_i(u_i)}{\alpha} + u_{min})}, & \text{if } 0 < y_i(u_i) < y_{sat}, \\ e^{-\lambda_x u_{max}} \delta(y_i(u_i) - y_{sat}), & \text{if } y_i(u_i) = y_{sat}, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $y_{sat} = \alpha(u_{max} - u_{min})$. The ML detector optimally combines the output from each rectifier and takes the final decision, based on the criterion

$$\prod_{i=1}^N f(y_i|u_i^0) \stackrel{\tilde{x}=0}{\geq} \prod_{i=1}^N f(y_i|u_i^1). \quad (6)$$

III. SYMBOL ERROR RATE ANALYSIS

A. Multiple Rectennas (MRCA)

As seen in Fig. 1, the decoder samples and optimally combines, the DC outputs from N rectennas. Therefore, the relative decoding complexity is equal to 3^N , and the total probability of error follows.

Theorem 1. *The total probability of error for MRCA is*

$$P_e^{\text{MRCA}} = \sum_{S=0}^N \binom{N}{S} P_{e_1}(S, L, M) + \sum_{S=0}^{N-1} N \binom{N-1}{S} P_{e_2}(S, L, M) + \sum_{\substack{S=0 \\ 2 \leq L \leq N}}^{N-L} \binom{N}{L} \binom{N-L}{S} P_{e_3}(S, L, M), \quad (7)$$

where $S, L, M \in [0, N]$ denote the number of rectennas whose DC output is in the sensitivity, linear and saturation

area, respectively, and their sum is equal to N . $P_{e_1}(S, L, M)$, $P_{e_2}(S, L, M)$, $P_{e_3}(S, L, M)$, are given in Appendix A.

Proof. Appendix A. \square

B. Multiple Rectifiers (MRCE)

Considering the steps from [8], we calculate the optimum number of rectifiers activated, based on the received power signal. Specifically, all the rectifiers, need to overpass the sensitivity level of input power in order to be activated, i.e. $u_1 > N_o u_{min}$. Furthermore, the optimum number of activated rectifiers N_o , should maximize the EH, avoiding the saturation effect, i.e. $\alpha(u_1 - N_o u_{min}) > (N_o - 1)y_{sat}$. Finally, in order to avoid activating more than N_o rectifiers that will degrade the EH efficiency due to shifted turn on power, the following condition should be met $N_o u_{max} \geq \alpha(u_1 - (N_o + 1)u_{min})$. Consequently, N_o is given by

$$N_o = \left\lceil \frac{u_1 - u_{min}}{u_{max}} \right\rceil. \quad (8)$$

As seen in Fig.2, the decoder in order to estimate the transmitted symbol \tilde{x} , considers only one DC output out of the N_o activated rectifiers. Therefore, the decoding complexity is equal to 3, while the ML criterion is given from (6), for $N = 1$,

$$u_1 \underset{\tilde{x}=0}{\overset{\tilde{x}=1}{\geq}} \frac{1}{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_0)} \ln \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_0}, \quad (9)$$

where K is set equal to the right part of the inequality. The total probability of error for MRCE scheme follows.

Theorem 2. *The total probability of error for MRCE is*

$$P_e^{\text{MRCE}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - e^{-\lambda_1 u_{min}} + e^{-N_R \lambda_0 u_{max}} + N_R (e^{-\lambda_0 k} - e^{-\lambda_1 k}) \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R} e^{-\lambda_1 ((N_o-1)u_{max} + u_{min})} - e^{-\lambda_0 N_o u_{max}} \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R-1} e^{-N_o \lambda_{\tilde{x}'} u_{max}} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{\tilde{x}'} u_{min}}) \right], \quad (10)$$

where \tilde{x}' denotes the symbol that was not estimated,

Proof. See Appendix B. \square

C. Asymptotic Analysis

For $P \rightarrow \infty$, lower bounds, are calculated for both schemes.

Proposition 1. *The lower bounds for the MRCA and MRCE schemes, are given by*

$$P_{bound}^{\text{MRCA}} = \lim_{P \rightarrow \infty} P_e^{\text{MRCA}} = \frac{1}{2} e^{-N \lambda_0 u_{max}}. \quad (11)$$

$$P_{bound}^{\text{MRCE}} = \lim_{P \rightarrow \infty} P_e^{\text{MRCE}} = \frac{1}{2} e^{-N_R \lambda_0 u_{max}}. \quad (12)$$

Proof. (11) follows from (19) in Appendix A, considering that $L = 0$, $M = 0$ and $t > 0$. Furthermore, (12) follows from (25) in Appendix B, considering that the received power signal, u_1 , activates the N_R rectifiers, in the saturation area. \square

We notice that the two schemes, provide the same performance in terms of SER, given that $N = N_R$ and $P \rightarrow \infty$.

IV. AVERAGE ENERGY HARVESTED

In this section we present the average EH denoted by Q , for both schemes. Specifically, is calculated as the sum of expected values from all the DC outputs. Therefore, for the MRCA scenario, is given by

$$Q^{\text{MRCA}} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha N \sum_{x \in (0,1)} \frac{e^{-\lambda_x u_{min}} - e^{-\lambda_x u_{max}}}{\lambda_x}. \quad (13)$$

The total average EH for the MRCE scenario, is given by

$$Q^{\text{MRCE}} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha \sum_{x \in (0,1)} \left[N_R l_4 e^{-\lambda_x N_R u_{max}} + l_4 \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R-1} N_o (e^{-\lambda_x l_2} - e^{-\lambda_x l_3}) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{\lambda_x} \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R} \left(e^{-\lambda_x l_2} (\lambda_x N_o u_{min} - l_2 \lambda_x - 1) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - e^{-\lambda_x l_1} (\lambda_x N_o u_{min} - l_1 \lambda_x - 1) \right) \right], \quad (14)$$

where $l_1 = (N_o - 1)u_{max} + u_{min}$, $l_2 = N_o u_{max}$ and $l_3 = N_o u_{max} + u_{min}$, denoting the limits that the received power signal u_1 ranges, when in linear and saturation area and considering that $N_o \in [1, N_R]$. Also, $l_4 = u_{max} - u_{min}$.

For $P \rightarrow \infty$, an upper bound is derived for both schemes.

$$Q_{bound}^{\text{MRCA}} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha N \left(\frac{e^{-\lambda_0 u_{min}} - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{max}}}{\lambda_0} + l_4 \right). \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{bound}^{\text{MRCE}} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha \left[l_4 N_R (1 + e^{-\lambda_0 N_R u_{max}}) \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R} e^{-\lambda_0 N_o u_{max}} \left(l_4 ((N_o - 1)e^{\lambda_0 l_4} - N_o) - \frac{(1 - e^{\lambda_0 l_4})}{\lambda_0} \right) \right. \\ \left. + l_4 (1 - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{min}}) \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R-1} N_o e^{-\lambda_0 N_o u_{max}} \right], \quad (16)$$

where (15) and (16) follow from (13) and (14), considering that $\lambda_1 \rightarrow 0$ for $P \rightarrow \infty$, while for $x \rightarrow 0$, $\exp(-x) \approx 1 - x$.

V. NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we provide numerical and experimental results and illustrate the performance for MRCA and MRCE. We set $u_{min} = 0.1$ and $u_{max} = 2$, while conversion efficiency is considered $\alpha = 0.7$ [10]. Monte-Carlo simulations are carried out for 10^6 iterations. Fig. 3, presents the performance of the proposed schemes in terms of SER, considering $N = N_R = 2$. Furthermore, the case of $N = N_R = 1$, is presented as a benchmark. By increasing N and N_R , the performance is enhanced, while MRCA scenario outperforms MRCE, in low power regime. As $P \rightarrow \infty$, the two schemes perform the same. In Fig. 4, we illustrate the performance, in terms of EH. We notice that both schemes increase the EH, with MRCA scheme outperforming the MRCE. Finally, for low values of P , there is a higher divergence between the two schemes, due to shifted

Fig. 3. SER for the proposed MRCA and MRCE schemes.

Fig. 4. EH for the proposed MRCA and MRCE schemes.

turn on power caused from the multiple rectifiers in the MRCE scheme.

For the comparison with the theoretical model, the circuits for $N = 1, N_R = 1, 2$ were implemented using voltage doubler topologies. For $N_R = 2$, a $3dB$ Wilkinson power divider was used and for the single and dual branch rectifiers, a low loss substrate, Rogers RT/duroid 5880. Lumped components available in Colilcrafts ADS library were used to match the rectifiers in the ISM band. The implemented circuits can be seen in Fig. 5. For testing purpose, the *R&S SSMF100A* microwave signal generator was connected directly to the input of the circuit and was used to generate the input signals. The input OOK signal with AWGN was created from the generator and the rectified DC voltage was measured on the optimized ohmic load using a DMM. The efficiency was measured on the optimized load for $N = N_R = 1$ and for $N = 1$ and $N_R = 2$ when a voltage combiner, Fig. 6 topology was used for the termination load.

The measured results in Fig. 5, indicate that the efficiency depends on the input power non-linearly. As expected there is a peak value before the saturation voltage and subsequently, the efficiency drops rapidly. The nonlinear dependence of the efficiency with respect to the input power is the main cause of the discrepancies between the theoretical model which uses a fixed efficiency, $\alpha = 0.7$, and the measurements where the non-linearity of the efficiency prevails. Fig. 6 presents the simulated rectified DC power on selected termination

Fig. 5. Comparison of efficiencies.

Fig. 6. Output power of circuit for $N = 1, N_R = 1, 2$.

loads which has consistent behavior with the numerical results presented in Fig. 4. Eventually, after the saturation of the rectified voltage, the DC power for $N = 1, N_R = 2$ is approximately double the power for the $N = 1, N_R = 1$ case.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we study two coherent detection schemes for integrated SWIPT receivers. Firstly, we examine the MRCA scenario, considering a SIMO topology, with multiple rectennas at the receiver's side. Adopting, a non-linear EH model, we capture the sensitivity and saturation behavior of the rectifiers. With the use of a ML decoder and soft decoding, we exploit simultaneously the received DC power signal for EH and ID. In addition, we study the MRCE scheme, with one receive antenna connected to multiple rectifiers, targeting to reduce the decoding complexity. Both schemes, jointly enhance the EH and ID, with the MRCA scenario outperforming the MRCE. Simulation, experimental and theoretical results are consistent, corroborating our study.

APPENDIX A

Lemma 1. Considering that S DC outputs are in the sensitivity area, L in the linear and M in the saturation, the ML criterion for the MRCA scheme, is given from (6) as

$$(\lambda_1 - \lambda_0) \sum_{i=0}^L u_i \begin{matrix} \tilde{x}=0 \\ \geq \\ \tilde{x}=1 \end{matrix} (\lambda_0 - \lambda_1) u_{max} M + \ln \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_0} \right)^L + \ln \left(\frac{1 - e^{-\lambda_1 u_{min}}}{1 - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{min}}} \right)^S. \quad (17)$$

We set $z = \sum_{i=1}^L u_i$ and t equal to the right part of inequality. From (17), the probability of error for the MRCA scheme is

$$P_e^{\text{MRCA}} = \mathbb{P}(z < t | x = 0) + \mathbb{P}(z > t | x = 1). \quad (18)$$

In order to proceed we identify the below cases.

$L = 0 \rightarrow z = 0$: Form Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{e_1}(S, L, M) &= \mathbb{P}(0 < t | x = 0) + \mathbb{P}(0 > t | x = 1) \\ &= \begin{cases} \mathbb{P}(x = 0) (\mathbb{P}(u < u_{\min}))^S (\mathbb{P}(u_{\max} \leq u))^M, & \text{if } t > 0, \\ \mathbb{P}(x = 1) (\mathbb{P}(u < u_{\min}))^S (\mathbb{P}(u_{\max} \leq u))^M, & \text{if } t < 0, \end{cases} \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} (1 - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{\min}})^S e^{-\lambda_0 u_{\max} M}, & \text{if } t > 0, \\ \frac{1}{2} (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\min}})^S e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\max} M}, & \text{if } t < 0, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where (a) follows from (1), considering that S DC outputs are in the sensitivity area and M in the saturation.

$L = 1 \rightarrow z = u_1$: From Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{e_2}(S, L, M) &= \mathbb{P}(z < t | x = 0) + \mathbb{P}(z > t | x = 1) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(x = 0) \mathbb{P}(u_{\min} \leq u_1 < t) (\mathbb{P}(u < u_{\min}))^S (\mathbb{P}(u_{\max} \leq u))^M \\ &\quad + \mathbb{P}(x = 1) \mathbb{P}(t \leq u_1 < u_{\max}) (\mathbb{P}(u < u_{\min}))^S (\mathbb{P}(u_{\max} \leq u))^M \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{=} \frac{1}{2} (e^{-\lambda_0 t} - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{\max}}) (1 - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{\min}})^S e^{-\lambda_0 u_{\max} M} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\min}} - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\min}})^S e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\max} M} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where (b) follows from (1).

$2 \leq L \leq N \rightarrow z = u_1 + \dots + u_N$: The probability of error for these events is denoted as $P_{e_3}(S, L, M)$.

Proposition 2. The probability of the event $\mathbb{P}(z < t)$ is

- If $Lu_{\min} \leq t < (L-1)u_{\min} + u_{\max}$

$$\mathbb{P}(z < t) \stackrel{(c)}{=} e^{-L\lambda_x u_{\min}} - (1 + \lambda_x t - L\lambda_x u_{\min}) e^{-\lambda_x t}, \quad (21)$$
- If $(L-1)u_{\min} + u_{\max} \leq t < Lu_{\max}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(z < t) &= \mathbb{P}(z) - \mathbb{P}(t \leq z < Lu_{\max}) \\ &\stackrel{(d)}{=} (e^{-\lambda_x u_{\min}} - e^{-\lambda_x u_{\max}})^L \\ &\quad - e^{-L\lambda_x u_{\max}} + (1 + \lambda_x t - L\lambda_x u_{\max}) e^{-\lambda_x t}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Proof. (c) and (d) follow considering that z follows the Erlang distribution. \square

From Lemma 1 and Proposition 2, $P_{e_3}(S, L, M)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} P_{e_3}(S, L, M) &= \mathbb{P}(x = 0) \mathbb{P}(z > t) (\mathbb{P}(u < u_{\min}))^S (\mathbb{P}(u_{\max} \leq u))^M \\ &\quad + \mathbb{P}(x = 1) \mathbb{P}(z < t) (\mathbb{P}(u < u_{\min}))^S (\mathbb{P}(u_{\max} \leq u))^M \\ &\bullet \text{ If } Lu_{\min} \leq t < (L-1)u_{\min} + u_{\max} \\ &\quad = \frac{1}{2} [e^{-L\lambda_0 u_{\max}} - e^{-\lambda_0 t} (1 + \lambda_0 t - L\lambda_0 u_{\max})] \\ &\quad \quad (1 - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{\min}})^S e^{-M\lambda_0 u_{\max}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} [e^{-L\lambda_1 u_{\min}} - e^{-\lambda_1 t} (1 + \lambda_1 t - L\lambda_1 u_{\min})] \\ &\quad \quad (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\min}})^S e^{-M\lambda_1 u_{\max}}, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

- If $(L-1)u_{\min} + u_{\max} \leq t < Lu_{\max}$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{2} [e^{-L\lambda_0 u_{\max}} - e^{-\lambda_0 t} (1 + \lambda_0 t - L\lambda_0 u_{\max})] \\ &\quad (1 - e^{-\lambda_0 u_{\min}})^S e^{-M\lambda_0 u_{\max}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} [(e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\min}} - e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\max}})^L \\ &\quad \quad - e^{-L\lambda_1 u_{\max}} + e^{-\lambda_1 t} (1 + \lambda_1 t - L\lambda_1 u_{\max})] \\ &\quad \quad (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 u_{\min}})^S e^{-M\lambda_1 u_{\max}}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

APPENDIX B

With the same steps as in Appendix A and from (9)

$$\begin{aligned} P_e^{\text{MRCE}} &= \mathbb{P}(u_1 > k | x = 0) + \mathbb{P}(u_1 < k | x = 1) \\ &\stackrel{(e)}{=} \mathbb{P}(u_1 < u_{\min} | x = 1) + \mathbb{P}(u_1 > N_R u_{\max} | x = 0) \\ &\stackrel{(f)}{+} \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R} \mathbb{P}((N_o - 1)u_{\max} + u_{\min} \leq u_1 < k | x = 0) \\ &\quad + \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R} \mathbb{P}(k \leq u_1 < N_o u_{\max} | x = 1) \\ &\stackrel{(g)}{+} \sum_{N_o=1}^{N_R-1} \mathbb{P}(N_o u_{\max} \leq u_1 < N_o u_{\max} + u_{\min} | x = \tilde{x}'), \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where (e) follows considering that the u_1 is in the sensitivity area, (f) in the linear and (g) in the saturation. With the use of (1) and the appropriate calculations, (10) is derived.

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